

Herpes simplex virus type 1 is the cause of Alzheimer's disease

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Abstract

Objective: The possible involvement of viruses, specifically Herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1), in senile dementia of the Alzheimer type has been investigated by numerous publications. Over 120 publications are providing direct or indirect evidence of a potential relationship between Herpes simplex virus type 1 and Alzheimer's disease (AD) but a causal relation is still not established yet.

Methods: A systematic review and re-analysis of studies which investigated the relationship between HSV-1 and AD by HSV-1 immunoglobulin G (IgG) serology and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) methods was conducted. The method of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship (SINE) was used to proof the hypothesis: *without* HSV-1 infection of human brain *no* AD. The method of the *conditio per quam* relationship (IMP) was used to proof the hypothesis: *if* HSV-1 infection of human brain *then* AD. The mathematical formula of the *causal relationship* k was used to proof the hypotheses is, whether there is a cause-effect relationship between HSV-1 and AD. Significance was indicated by a p-value of less than 0.05.

Results: The studies analyzed were able to provide strict evidence that HSV-1 is a necessary condition (a *conditio sine qua non*), a sufficient condition and a necessary and sufficient condition of AD. Furthermore, the cause-effect relationship between HSV-1 and AD was highly significant.

Conclusions: The data analyzed provide sufficient evidence to conclude that HSV-1 is the cause of AD.

Keywords: Herpes simplex virus type 1, Alzheimer's disease, causal relationship.

1. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (Alzheimer, 1906, 1907) defined by *Alois Alzheimer* (1864-1915) at the “37. *Versammlung Südwestdeutscher Irrenärzte*“ or 37th Meeting of South-West German Psychiatrists (Hippius and Neundörfer, 2003; Drouin and Drouin, 2017) held in Tübingen on November 3, 1906 is by far one of the most devastating brain disorders of elderly humans. Alzheimer's disease is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by a subtle clinical presentation while the progressive decline in cognitive functions is leading to memory loss and dementia. In 2010, about 35.5 million individuals were affected by dementia in the world (Piacentini *et al.*, 2014). More than 20 different risk factors (Henderson, 1988) for Alzheimer's disease, including age, lifestyle, familial inheritance (Kim *et al.*, 2009), exposure to aluminium, traumatic brain injury (TBI), associated vascular and other co-morbidities and infection have been discussed in the literature (Armstrong, 2019) to determine to a high degree the occurrence (Imtiaz *et al.*, 2014) of dementia and Alzheimer's disease, the leading cause of dementia. Especially *Herpes simplex virus type 1*, a highly neurotropic double-stranded DNA virus, is repeatedly implicated in AD pathology by an increasing number of reports. The majority of the world-wide human population is infected with herpes simplex virus type 1. The seroprevalence (Shen *et al.*, 2015) of Herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) was published as 63.2% and 7.7% for genital herpes, caused usually by Herpes simplex virus type 2 (HSV-2). During a typical primary infection, HSV-1 spreads from the oral pharynx to the trigeminal ganglia, where a latent HSV-1 infection for the entire life of the host is established followed by periodic reactivations. This is not the only path (Burgos *et al.*, 2005) through which the reactivated HSV-1 virus may infect the brain (Kastrukoff *et al.*, 1982, Jamieson *et al.*, 1991a; Schmutzhard, 2001; Lewandowski *et al.*, 2002) without causing observable neurologic signs. However, a rare but severe and most fatal viral encephalitis can occur too, the Herpes simplex encephalitis (Sekizawa and Openshaw, 1984; Steiner, 2011). Herpes simplex encephalitis (HSE) is one of the most devastating disorders caused by Herpes simplex. The prognosis of HSE is dependent on early diagnosis and effective therapy. Meanwhile, HSV-1 infection (Ball, 1982) has been linked to Alzheimer's disease (De Chiara *et al.*, 2012; Piacentini *et al.*, 2014; Itzhaki, 2017) too, even if the underlying molecular and

functional mechanisms have not been fully elucidated yet. HSV-1 DNA has been discovered to reside in a high proportion of brains of elderly people in latent form (Jamieson *et al.*, 1991b) while HSV-1 DNA was present only in a very small proportion of brains of very young people and children (Wozniak *et al.*, 2005, 2009b). However, the increase in life expectancy is still regarded as the main risk factor for AD. Neuropathologically, the brain of Alzheimer's disease sufferer is characterized by the presence of extracellular amyloid plaques composed of amyloid- β protein (A β) and intraneuronal neurofibrillary tangles composed of hyperphosphorylated Tau protein (Kosik *et al.*, 1986). People surviving HSE showed clinical signs of AD (i.e., cognitive impairment and memory loss) which provided some evidence suggesting (Ball, 1982) the involvement of HSV-1 in AD. Meanwhile, studies are providing some solid support of the involvement of HSV-1 infection in AD pathogenesis. In Alzheimer's disease brains, Wozniak *et al.* (Wozniak *et al.*, 2009b) reported that about 90% of the Alzheimer's disease plaques contained the HSV-1 DNA (Wozniak *et al.*, 2009a). Other studies conducted demonstrated the relationship between AD and HSV-1 infection by searching for antibodies (Letenneur *et al.*, 2008; Kobayashi *et al.*, 2013, Mancuso *et al.*, 2014b) and other against HSV-1 in the blood of AD patients. Several reviews and meta-analysis (Steel and Eslick, 2015; Harris and Harris, 2018, Itzhaki, 2018b; Tzeng *et al.*, 2018) investigated whether research data are supporting the hypothesis that brain infections by herpes simplex virus type 1 are causally related with AD and published controversy results. Especially, the 57 studies review and meta-analysis by Warren-Gash *et al.* (Warren-Gash *et al.*, 2019) found for HSV-1 no evidence that DNA in the brain was associated with dementia though quality across the 57 included studies was very low. Nevertheless, the potential pathogenetic link between HSV1 infection AD remains unclear (Olsson *et al.*, 2016; Pisa *et al.*, 2017).

2. Material and methods

The studies meta-analyzed preferred to use its own terminology, its own kits, its own primers et cetera to describe scientific discoveries with respect to AD. The results of these studies are aggravated especially by missing a uniform operational definition of HSV-1 positivity and standardization in general. Finally, besides of the use of different methodological approaches and other factors which are a potential source of bias, the studies were able to agree on certain

points.

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Search Strategy

Google Scholar and the database PubMed was search for research articles pertaining to infection and AD using some suitable key words like “Herpes simplex type 1”, “Alzheimer’s disease”, PCR or IgG et cetera conducted in any country which investigated the relationship between HSV-1 and AD by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technology or serum HSV-1 IgG. There was no financial support for this study. Therefore, only studies with data publicly available were formally considered for a review. In general, 18 PCR based studies (Roberts *et al.*, 1986; Deatly *et al.*, 1990, Jamieson *et al.*, 1991b, 1992; Kittur *et al.*, 1992; Bertrand, 1993; Lin *et al.*, 1996, 1998, 2002; Itabashi *et al.*, 1997; Itzhaki *et al.*, 1997; Beffert *et al.*, 1998; Cheon *et al.*, 2001; Hemling *et al.*, 2003, Mori *et al.*, 2004, Wozniak *et al.*, 2009b; Olsson *et al.*, 2016) were identified, while the study design of almost all PCR based studies was very inappropriate. IgG seropositivity was studied by 15 studies, including the studies of Barnes *et al.* and Wozniak *et al.* (Wozniak *et al.*, 2005; Barnes *et al.*, 2015).

Table 1. *The article selection process of the studies analyzed*

1. Identification of records	Size	Total
Records identified by searching in the databases		
PubMed	137	
Google Scholar	958	
Additional records identified from review articles		
Harris and Harris, 2018	278	
Warren-Gash <i>et al.</i> , 2019	83	1456
2. Clean-up of search (Screening)		
Records removed after verifying duplication, excluded by title, excluded due to other reasons		1423
3. Eligibility		
Articles evaluated for eligibility		33
Articles excluded for various reasons		
Data were self-contradictory	6	
Data are not appropriate enough	4	
Data access barriers	13	
4. Included		
Articles included in the meta-analysis (Table 2, 4, 5, 6)		10

Adopted from PRISMA 2009 (Moher *et al.*, 2009).

2.1.2. HSV-1 IgG-Studies considered for re-analysis

The following HSV-1 IgG sero-epidemiological studies (Letenneur *et al.*, 2008, Mancuso *et al.*, 2014a, b, Lövheim *et al.*, 2015a, b, Agostini *et al.*, 2016b, b) as presented by **Table 2** were considered for meta-analysis.

Table 2. Without HSV-1 IgG sero-positivity no AD.

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P	Case_T	Con_P	Con_T	p(SINE)	X ² (SINE B)	X ² (SINE A)	k	P value (k)	IOU	IOI
			(a)	(a+c)	(b)	(b+d)							
Letenneur <i>et al.</i>	2008	490	69	77	335	413	0,984	0,831	0,744	0,081	0,046	0,018	0,667
Lövheim <i>et al.</i>	2014	3432	213	227	2813	3205	0,996	0,863	0,483	0,047	0,002	0,052	0,816
Mancuso <i>et al.</i>	2014	134	81	83	50	51	0,985	0,048	1,333	-0,015	0,766	0,597	0,358
Mancuso <i>et al.</i>	2014	157	83	83	71	74	1,000	0,000	0,000	0,148	0,102	0,510	0,452
Lövheim <i>et al.</i>	2015	720	338	360	324	360	0,969	1,344	8,345	0,071	0,037	0,419	0,419
Agostini <i>et al.</i>	2016	120	57	59	60	61	0,983	0,068	1,333	-0,056	0,884	0,467	0,483
Total		5053	841	889	3653	4164		3,155	12,238			0,344	0,533

Alpha = 0,050

Degrees of freedom = 6

Chi square (critical) = 12,592

Chi square (calculated) = 3,155 12,238

Case_P: case, positive; Case_T: case total; Con_P: healthy control positive; Con_T: healthy control total.

The studies of Mancuso *et al.* (Mancuso *et al.*, 2014b) and Agostini *et al.* (Agostini *et al.*, 2016b) were considered for meta-analysis in this context although the study design of both studies was very problematic. Several HSV-1 IgG and other HSV IgG studies (Ounanian *et al.*, 1990; Wozniak *et al.*, 2005; Féart *et al.*, 2011; Kobayashi *et al.*, 2013; Barnes *et al.*, 2015; Bu *et al.*, 2015, Agostini *et al.*, 2016a, 2018; Pandey *et al.*, 2019) were not considered for meta-analysis, while some of those studies are viewed by **Table 3**. Several studies had data access barriers, provided inappropriate data or provided self-contradictory data (Barukčić,

2019f).

Table 3. HSV-1 IgG studies not considered for re-analyses.

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P (a)	Case_T (a+c)	Con_P (b)	Con_T (b+d)
Bu et al.	2015	263	0	128	0	135
Ounanian et al.	1990	40	0	19	0	21
Pandey et al.	2019	93	0	56	0	37
Agostini et al.	2016	0	0	0	0	0
Barnes et al.	2015	0	0	0	0	0
Féart et al.	2011	0	0	0	0	0
Kobayashi et al.	2013	0	0	0	0	0

2.1.3. PCR-Studies considered for meta-analysis

Studies which detected HSV-1 DNA in postmortem brain tissues from patients with AD and controls (non-neurological cases) by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) methods used different primers (glycoprotein D protein; thymidine kinase) for PCR. The quality of the source of amplification template was different. Rodriguez et al. (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2005) were able to provide evidence that DNA integrity decreases significantly with increasing time of storage in formalin. Due to this and other factors, PCR studies had very different HSV-1 detection rates. Hemling et al. (Hemling *et al.*, 2003) and Marques et al. (Marques *et al.*, 2001) detected HSV-1 DNA in a very low proportion of brains due to unknown reasons while the access to the data of the study of Marques et al. (Marques *et al.*, 2001) was not possible. Besides of an inappropriate study design, it was possible to calculate the *conditio sine qua non* relationship of the studies of Jamieson et al. (Jamieson *et al.*, 1991a, b) and Cheon et al. (Cheon *et al.*, 2001). However, besides of the difficulties mentioned, to many studies were able to provide the impressive detection rates. The PCR studies (Jamieson *et al.*, 1991b, 1992; Cheon *et al.*, 2001; Mori *et al.*, 2004) which supported the *conditio sine qua non relationship* between HSV-1 and AD are listed by the following table (Table 4).

Table 4. Without HSV-1 PCR DNA positivity no AD (according to PCR studies).

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P (a)	Case_T (a+c)	Con_P (b)	Con_T (b+d)	p(SINE)	X ² (SINE Bt)	k	IOU	IOI
Jamieson et al.	1992	36	14	21	9	15	0,806	2,333	+0,068	0,222	0,056
Mori et al.	2004	9	3	3	1	6	1,000	0,000	+0,791	0,222	0,111
Jamieson et al.	1991	14	8	8	6	6	1,000	0,000	-	0,571	0,429
Cheon et al.	2001	20	10	10	10	10	1,000	0,000	-	0,500	0,500

The PCR studies (Jamieson *et al.*, 1991b, 1992; Cheon *et al.*, 2001; Mori *et al.*, 2004) which provided evidence of a *conditio per quam relationship* between HSV-1 and AD are listed by the following table (Table 5).

Table 5. If HSV-1 PCR DNA positivity then AD (according to PCR studies).

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P (a)	Case_T (a+c)	Con_P (b)	Con_T (b+d)	p(IMP)	X ² (IMP At)	k	IOU	IOI
Itabashi et al.	1997	69	14	46	5	23	0,928	1,316	+0,092	0,058	0,391
Mori et al.	2004	9	3	3	1	6	0,889	0,250	+0,791	0,222	0,111

The study of Mori et. al., (2004)

The only PCR based study which provided evidence of a *conditio sine qua non relationship*, of *conditio per quam relationship*, of a *conditio sine qua non and conditio per quam relationship* and of a significant cause effect relationship was the study of Mori et al. (Mori *et al.*, 2004). The sample size was n = 9 and the P value was calculated according to Fisher's exact test (Table 6).

Table 6. The study of Mori et. al., (2004).

		Alzheimer's disease		
		Yes	No	
HSV-1 (PCR DNA)	Yes	3	1	4
	No	0	5	5
		3	6	9

Statistical analysis (Table 6).

Causal relationship k =	+0,791	95 % CI (k): (0,045 -	1,000)	IOU =	-0,222
P value (k Fisher's test) =	0,04762	Chi Sq.(k) =	5,625	IOI =	0,111
				p(IOU) + p(IOI) =	0,333
p (SINE) =	1,000	Chi Sq. 1(SINE) =	0,000	Chi Sq. 2(SINE) =	0,000
p (IMP) =	0,889	Chi Sq. 1(IMP) =	0,167	Chi Sq. 2(IMP) =	0,250

p (SINE ^IMP) =	0,889	Chi Sq. 1(SINE ^IMP) =	0,167	Chi Sq. 2(SINE ^IMP) =	0,250
p (EXCL) =	0,667	Chi Sq. 1(EXCL) =	3,000	Chi Sq. 2(EXCL) =	2,250

2.2. Methods

Definition 1. (The Binomial distribution)

The binomial distribution is defined by the Suisse mathematician Jacob Bernoulli (1655 - 1705) in his work *Ars Conjectandi* (Bernoulli, 1713) as

$$p(X = x) = \left(\frac{n!}{x! \times (n - x)!} \right) \pi(x_t)^x \times (1 - \pi(x_t))^{n-x} \quad (1)$$

where $p(X = x)$ is the probability mass function of observing exactly x successes in n trials, with the probability of success on a single trial denoted by $\pi(x_t)$ and $q(x_t) = 1 - \pi(x_t)$. There is evidence that $0!=1!$ (Barukčić, 2019a, p. 195) is not correct. Therefore, the binomial distribution should be used for values $n \geq 2$ and $1 \leq x \leq n - 1$. For values $n = 1$ or $n = x$ or $x = 0$, the generalized Bernoulli distribution should be used. The generalized *Bernoulli distribution* is defined as

$$p(X = x) = \pi(x_t)^x \times (1 - \pi(x_t))^{n-x} \quad (2)$$

In the case $n = 1$, the same reduces to the simple Bernoulli distribution defined as

$$p(X = x) = \pi(x_t)^x \times (1 - \pi(x_t))^{1-x} \quad (3)$$

Under conditions where $x = n$ we obtain

$$p(X = n) = \pi(x_t)^n \times (1 - \pi(x_t))^{n-n} = \pi(x_t)^n \quad (4)$$

Under conditions where $x = 0$ we obtain

$$p(X = 0) = \pi(x_t)^0 \times (1 - \pi(x_t))^{n-0} = (1 - \pi(x_t))^n \quad (5)$$

CLAIM.

Under some circumstances, the *proportion or the probability* $p(X = n)$ is given approximately by the formula

$$p(X = n) = e^{-E(X)} \quad (6)$$

PROOF.

In general, under conditions above where $X = n$, it is

$$p(X = n) = \pi(x_t)^n \tag{7}$$

In particular, it is $\pi(x_t) = 1 - q(x_t)$. Substituting, we obtain

$$p(X = n) = (1 - q(x_t))^n \tag{8}$$

or

$$p(X = n) = \left(1 - \frac{n \times q(x_t)}{n}\right)^n \tag{9}$$

We define $E(\underline{X}) = n \times q(x_t)$. The equation before simplifies as

$$p(X = n) = \left(1 - \frac{E(\underline{X})}{n}\right)^n \tag{10}$$

Increasing the number of randomly generated variables (sample size n grows) enable us to take the limit. In point of fact, taking the limit of the term

$$\left(1 - \left(\frac{E(\underline{X})}{n}\right)\right)^n \tag{11}$$

as the number of (Bernoulli) trials or the sample size n goes to positive infinity ($n \rightarrow +\infty$),

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\left(1 - \left(\frac{E(\underline{X})}{n}\right)\right)^n \right) \tag{12}$$

we obtain according to the known elementary calculus (DeGroot *et al.*, 2005)

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\left(1 - \left(\frac{E(\underline{X})}{n}\right)\right)^n \right) = e^{-E(\underline{X})} \tag{13}$$

Thus far, as the sample size increases or as the number of trials n goes to positive infinity ($n \rightarrow +\infty$) the equation above simplifies as

$$p(X = n) = e^{-E(\underline{X})} \tag{14}$$

QUOD ERAT DEMONSTRANDUM.

For greater sample size, the left tailed P Value of $(X \leq n-1)$ can be calculated as

$$p(X \leq n - 1) \equiv 1 - e^{-E(\underline{X})} \tag{15}$$

2.2.2. Data analysis

The causal relationship k (Hessen, 1928; Korch, 1965; Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2016a, b, 2017, 2018b, 2019e; Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016) was used to proof the data for a causal relationship while the significance was tested by the hypergeometric distribution (HGD) and the chi-square distribution (Pearson, 1900). The *conditio sine qua non* (Barukčić, 2018d, 1989, 1997, 2017, 2018b, a, 2019e; Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016) relationship (SINE) was used to proof the hypothesis, *without HSV-1 infection no AD*. The *conditio per quam* (Barukčić, 2018d, 1989, 1997, 2017, 2018b, a, 2019e; Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016) relationship (IMP) was used to proof the hypothesis, *if HSV-1 infection then AD*. The *necessary and sufficient condition* (Barukčić, 2018d, 1989, 1997, 2017, 2018b, a, 2019e; Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016) relationship (SINE and IMP) was used to proof the hypothesis, (*without HSV-1 infection no AD*) **and** (*if HSV-1 infection then AD*). The index of independence (Barukčić, 2019g) and the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019f) were used to control publication bias. All statistical analyses (Barukčić, 2019b, c) were performed with Microsoft® Excel® for Mac® version 16.2 (181208) software (© 2018, Microsoft GmbH, Munich, Germany). The level of significance was set to 0.05.

3. Results

THEOREM 1. WITHOUT HERPES SIMPLEX TYPE 1 IGG SERO-POSITIVITY NO ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HSV-1 IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of AD.

Alternative Hypothesis: HSV-1 IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of AD.

PROOF.

Several studies considered for meta-analysis (**Table 2**) provided convincing evidence of a *conditio sine qua non* relationship between HSV-1 and AD. The study of Lövheim et al. (Lövheim *et al.*, 2015a) with a sample size of $n = 3432$ was able to publish data with a sample proportion of $p((\text{HSV} - 1) \leftarrow (\text{AD})) = 0,996$ of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship (P Value = 0,002495376). At the same time, it was possible to determine the Chi-square values this study as Chi Sq. 1(SINE) = 0,004 and Chi Sq. 2(SINE) = 0,863. Altogether, the studies re-analyzed had a sample size of $n = 5053$. The studies of Mancuso et al. 2014 with

n=134 and of Agostini et al. 2016 with n=120 were considered for meta-analysis too. However, it cannot be excluded that the data of these studies are self-contradictory. The critical Chi-Square value (degrees of freedom = 6, $\alpha = 0,05$) of the 6 studies was 12,592. The calculated Chi-Square value was 3,155. In toto, it was not possible to reject the null-hypothesis: **without** a Herpes simplex type 1 IgG positivity **no** Alzheimer's disease. Herpes simplex type 1 IgG positivity is a necessary condition of Alzheimer's disease.

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THEOREM 2. IF HERPES SIMPLEX TYPE 1 PCR DNA POSTMORTEM POSITIVITY THEN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem positivity is a sufficient condition of AD.

Alternative Hypothesis: HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem positivity is not a sufficient condition of AD.

PROOF.

The HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem studies presented by **Table 5** provided evidence of a sufficient condition relationship between HSV-1 and AD. However, the sample size with n=78 is small. The study of Mori et al. 2004 was analyzed by Fisher's exact test too. Following the post-mortem HSV-1 PCR DNA studies, HSV-1 PCR DNA positivity is a sufficient condition for AD. In other words, **if** HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem positivity **then** AD.

QUOD ERAT DEMONSTRANDUM.

THEOREM 3. HERPES SIMPLEX TYPE 1 PCR DNA POSTMORTEM POSITIVITY IS A NECESSARY AND SUFFICIENT CONDITION OF AD

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem positivity is a necessary and sufficient condition of AD.

Alternative-Hypothesis: HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem positivity is not a necessary and sufficient condition of AD.

PROOF.

The study of Mori et al. 2004 (Mori *et al.*, 2004), analyzed by Fisher's exact test too, provided evidence of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship (**Table 6**) between HSV-1 and AD ($n = 9$; $p(\text{necessary and sufficient condition between HSV-1 and AD}) = 0,889$; $\text{Chi Sq. 1}(\text{SINE} \wedge \text{IMP}) = 0,167$; $\text{Chi Sq. 2}(\text{SINE} \wedge \text{IMP}) = 0,167$). The study design of the study of Mori et al. 2004 was very impressive ($p(\text{IOU}) + p(\text{IOI}) = 0,090909091$). Based on HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem study of Mori et al. 2004, HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem positivity is a necessary and sufficient condition of AD.

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THEOREM 4. HSV-1 IS THE CAUSE OF AD

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HSV-1 is not the cause of AD ($k = 0$).

Alternative Hypothesis: HSV-1 is the cause of AD ($k \neq 0$).

PROOF.

The HSV-1 IgG based study of Lövheim et al., 2015 (Lövheim *et al.*, 2015a) provided evidence of a significant cause-effect relationship (Causal relationship $k = +0,047$; $P \text{ value } (k / \text{HGD}) = 0,002495376$; $n = 3432$; $\text{Chi Sq.}(k) = 7,472$; d. f. = 1). The HSV-1 IgG based study of Letenneur et al., 2008 (Letenneur *et al.*, 2008) provided evidence of a significant cause-effect relationship (Causal relationship $k = +0,081$; $P \text{ value } (k / \text{HGD}) = 0,046$; $n = 490$) too. The second HSV-1 IgG based study of Lövheim et al., 2015 (Lövheim *et al.*, 2015b) provided evidence of a significant cause-effect relationship (causal relationship $k = +0,071$; $P \text{ value } (k / \text{HGD}) = 0,046$). The HSV-1 PCR DNA postmortem based study of Mori et al., 2004 provided evidence of a significant cause-effect relationship between HSV-1 and AD too (causal relationship $k = +0,833$; $P \text{ value } (k / \text{HGD}) = 0,01299$). In toto, studies with a sample size of $n = 4642$ provided evidence of a significant cause-effect relationship between HSV-1 and AD. As demonstrated before, HSV-1 is a necessary condition of AD, HSV-1 is a sufficient condition of AD and HSV-1 is a necessary and sufficient condition of AD. The evidence is overwhelming. **Herpes simplex type 1 is the cause of Alzheimer's disease.**

QUOD ERAT DEMONSTRANDUM.

4. Discussion

Meanwhile, Dementia is a major global health problem and nearly 35.6 million people live worldwide (WHO, n.d.) with dementia. The prevalence has been reported up to 8% among those aged 65 or more (Tzeng *et al.*, 2018) and the incidence continues to rise (WHO, n.d.). Even if Dementia affects people in all countries, national programmes to address this problem are rarely in place. This study is the first study world-wide known which was able to provide clear evidence and to establish **a cause-effect relationship between HSV-1 and AD**. However, there are several limitations of this study too. First of all, not all patients with probable AD were diagnosed according to the same criteria (McKhann *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, the laboratory kits used were different and could have impact on quality of the study data. In contrast to potential bias, the results of *HSV-1 IgG sero-epidemiological studies* which provided evidence of a significant relationship between HSV-1 and AD cannot be ignored. Even if HSV-1 IgG itself should not be regarded as the cause of AD, HSV-1 IgG provides an evidence of an HSV-1 infection and is privileged by virtue of being less error prone compared to PCR based studies in this context. Although the study design of the *HSV-1 IgG sero-epidemiological studies* analyzed was more than unfair and less than optimal, these studies were able to document a significant relationship between HSV-1 and AD. In other words, according to the HSV-1 IgG sero-epidemiological studies *without* HSV-1 infection *no* AD. Especially the HSV-1 IgG sero-epidemiological study of Lövheim *et al.*, 2015 (Lövheim *et al.*, 2015a) provided evidence of a significant cause-effect relationship (causal relationship $k = +0,047$; P value (k / HGD) = 0,002495376; $n = 3432$; Chi Sq.(k) = 7,472; d. f. = 1) and cannot be ignored. The left-tailed P value $p(X \leq n-1)$ can be calculated (Barukčić, 2019d) as

$$p(X \leq n - 1) = \left(\frac{E(X_t)}{E(X_t)} \right) \times \left(e^{-\frac{E(X_t)}{n}} \right) = \left(\left(\frac{14}{3414} \right) \times \left(e^{-\frac{14}{3432}} \right) \right) = \mathbf{0,004079288} \quad (16)$$

In other words, the null hypothesis must be rejected (P Value = 0,004079288). According to the data of Lövheim *et al.* (Lövheim *et al.*, 2015a) **Herpes simplex type 1 is a necessary condition of Alzheimer's disease (P Value = 0,004079288)**. In point of fact, **without** a herpes simplex type 1 infection **no** Alzheimer's disease. The *conditio sine qua non* relationship between HSV-1 and AD may be due to chance only in about 4 out of 1000 cases. Using the z-score the critical value of the data of Lövheim *et al.* (Lövheim *et al.*, 2015a) can

be calculated approximately (Barukčić, 2019d) as

$$p(x_t)_{critical} = +1 - \frac{14 \times 14}{3,5 \times 3,5 \times 3432} = 0,99533800 \quad (17)$$

where the sample size is $n = 3432$, the number of not observed cases is $\underline{X} = 14$ cases and the z score $z = 3,5$. The probability value associated with $Z=3,5$ is **0,000232629**. The sample proportion calculated was 0,995920746. The critical value $p_{critical} = 0,99533800$ is less than the calculated value of the sample proportion ($p_{sample} = 0,995920746$). The result is significant (P Value = 0,000232629). It is worth to mention, that none of the *HSV-1 IgG sero-epidemiological studies* analyzed were able to provide evidence of a sufficient condition relationship between HSV-1 IgG and AD, which is logical too.

Several studies detected HSV-1 DNA in brain tissue from patients with AD and controls (non-neurological cases) using PCR while the study design was far from acceptable. The PCR technology itself can be very faulty (Bacich *et al.*, 2011) and the quality of the results of PCR based investigations depend on several factors (Khot and Fredricks, 2009). Besides of the difficulties due to the PCR method itself, the skill of the investigator, the potential contamination with previously amplified PCR products, the primers used, the quality of the specimen et cetera, the PCR based studies reanalyzed provided striking evidence of the relationship between HSV-1 and AD too. Furthermore, HSV-infected subjects had an almost 3-fold increased risk of developing dementia in comparison to the control group (Tzeng *et al.*, 2018). Drug studies could provide some evidence on the relationship between HSV-1 and AD. In other words, the usage of **anti-herpetic medications** in the treatment of HSV infections should be able to reduce the risk of **dementia**. Indeed, the study of Tzeng *et al.* (Tzeng *et al.*, 2018) was able to document a significant risk reduction of dementia (Itzhaki, 2018a) development in patients affected by HSV infections upon treatment with antiherpetic medications. Patients treated aggressively with antiherpetic medications (Tzeng *et al.*, 2018) had the relative risk of dementia reduced by a factor of 10 (Itzhaki and Lathe, 2018). HSV-1 IgG seropositive schizophrenia patients treated with *valacyclovir 1.5 g twice daily orally for 18 weeks* compared to HSV-1 IgG seronegative control group improved in working memory, verbal memory, and visual object learning compared with placebo group (Prasad *et al.*, 2013).

These and other studies which investigated antiviral drugs acting by different mechanisms (restricting viral replication, blocking viral entry into cells et cetera) support *the usage of antiviral drugs for the treatment of AD* (Itzhaki, 2016).

The potential usage of antiviral drugs like **acyclovir** (ACV) and **valacyclovir**, the bioactive form of ACV, to treat AD patients, might be most effective especially if combined with other antiviral measures (**intravenous immunoglobulin** (Wozniak and Itzhaki, 2013), **zinc** (Gordon *et al.*, 1975; Kümel *et al.*, 1990; Shishkov *et al.*, 1997; Hirano *et al.*, 2008; Qiu *et al.*, 2013), **vitamin C** (Lerner *et al.*, 2002, 2007; Mikirova and Hunninghake, 2014), **lithium** (Skinner *et al.*, 1980) et cetera). Much of the necessary work lies ahead for validating the relationship between HSV-1 and AD dementia in detail. In particular, further research and clinical trials like the one which is already ongoing in Sweden (Lovheim, 2018) are necessary to provide us with therapeutic possibilities to treat the very dangerous AD effectively. In addition, improved hygiene and cleanliness could be useful to prevent the massive spread of Alzheimer's disease too. However, viruses like HSV-1 and other too are not only pathogens (Moelling, 2013), **destroyer of human life's** and killers, viruses are **creators of new species**, intelligent designers, building genomes (Koonin, 2016) and major driver of human evolution (Darwin, 1859) too. Viral sequences can be found in the genomes of various organisms to a very great extent. On the long run, an active vaccination against HSV-1 is necessary but should consider such and other aspects too.

5. Conclusion

In summary, the results of this study demand us to accept that *a Herpes simplex type 1 infection is the cause of Alzheimer's disease*.

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Author Contributions

The author confirms being the sole contributor of this work and has approved it for

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. There are no conflict of interest exists according to the guidelines of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors.

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